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THE IMPORTANCE OF NATURE RESERVES AND SANCTUARIES IN THE SHEKI-ZAGATALA REGION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOTOURISM

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Abstract

There are special places for the purpose of preserving of natural resources in different regions of Azerbaijan. These include nature reserves and sanctuaries. The article discusses the nature reserves and sanctuaries and their activity in the Sheki-Zagatala region of our Republic. The aim of the article is also to study the role of these reserves and sanctuaries in the sector of ecotourism.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Sheki-Zagatala region, nature reserve, sanctuary, ecology, ecological tourism.

Introduction

The earth is made up of land and water. Nature is the basis of the world. Taking care of natural resources is of vital importance for human life. Unfortunately, humanity has long faced an environmental problem. In this sense, the role of natural phenomena and anthropogenic impacts are irreplaceable. Of course, it is very difficult for us to intervene in floods, avalanches, landslides, ravines and other destructive natural phenomena. However, it is possible to prevent anthropogenic impacts. Since the creator of anthropogenic influences is man himself. On this basis, the famous culturologist N.A. Berdyaev's remarks on the relationship between man and nature are very interesting. He divided the relationship between man and nature into four stages: first, overloading of man in nature, second, detachment from nature, confrontation and struggle with nature, third, the appeal to it to assimilate nature, and fourth, the spiritual restoration of nature. According to Berdyaev, human impact on the environment is very strong. Therefore, man is the only being who can stand up for nature. Thus, such impacts have led to a violation of the ecological balance in the world.

In general, the issue of nature protection has always been relevant in the human world. From ancient times, states have done much to care for nature. 2000 years ago, measures were taken in Rome to protect fruit trees, in 1343 in Dortmund, Germany, laws were passed on the landscaping of farmland and pastures, and in 1250 in England, strict requirements were set for the protection of bird species such as eagles and hawks. However, in the twentieth century, the work for the protection of nature intensified:

1) The International Commission for Nature Conservation was established in 1913 at the International Conference on Nature Conservation in Bern with the participation of 13 countries;

2) In 1923, "the International Congress for Nature Conservation" was held in Paris, the capital of France;

3) In 1933, "the London Treaty on the Protection of Plant and Animal Habitats in Africa" was signed;

4) The International Union for Conservation of Nature was established in 1948 in Fontainebleau, France under the auspices of UNESCO;

5) At the end of the 1980s and at the beginning of the 1990s the concept of sustainability were further developed by the Brundtland report (1987) and the Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in 1992 etc. (Manafova M.C. et al, 2010, pp. 25; Muzaffer Yucel, Deniz Babushdogu, 2005, pp. 6, 8; Jorge Martín García & Julio Diez Casero, 2012, pp 4).

Thus, the implementation of such measures around the world and the continuation of this work today provides protection of the greenery of mankind. Among these special measures, the establishment of nature reserves and sanctuaries is very important.

Concepts of nature reserve and sanctuary

Nature reserves and sanctuaries are areas specially protected by the state. The main purpose of the organization of these areas is the protection of natural objects and complexes, as well as the preservation of their biological diversity, restoration of forests, protection and reproduction of rare and endangered animal species. In addition, the reserves are a major laboratory for the development of science. Scientific research is being conducted in these areas. In nature reserves, certain researches are usually carried out to study the regularities of natural phenomena and the diversity of the ecological system. Of course, the use of natural resources in the area, including bio and zoo environments, for economic purposes, as well as any activity that could damage any of their components, is strictly prohibited.

There are many reserves and sanctuaries in the world. Some of them are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List: Atlantic Forest South-East Reserves, Discovery Coast Atlantic Forest Reserves (Brazil), Srebarna Nature Reserve (Bulgaria), Dja Faunal Reserve (Cameroon), Rio Platano Biosphere Reserve (Honduras), Tsingy de Bemaraha Strict Nature Reserve (Madagascar), Vallée de Mai Nature Reserve (Seychelles), Central Suriname Nature Reserve (Suriname), Sichuan Giant Panda Sanctuaries-Wolong, Mt Siguniang and Jiain Mountains, Migratory Bird Sanctuaries along the Coast of Yellow Sea-Bohai Gulf of China (China), Malpelo Fauna and Flora Sanctuary (Colombia), Manas Wildlife Sanctuary (India), Mount Hamiguitan Range Wildlife Sanctuary (Philippines), Thungyai-Huai Kha Khaeng Wildlife Sanctuaries (Thailand) etc. (Nature reserves Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/tebii-servetlerimiz/qoruqlar>; Sanctuaries Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/tebii-servetlerimiz/yasaqliqlar>; World Heritage List Retrieved from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/?type=natural>).

History of formation and natural resources of the nature reserves organized in Sheki-Zagatala region

Nature reserves have been established in various regions of Azerbaijan as well as in the world. The landscape, vegetation and fauna of these areas, which are intended for nature protection, differ from each other. Examples of nature reserves in Azerbaijan are Pirgulu State Nature Reserve, Ismayilli State Nature Reserve, Garayazi State Nature Reserve, Shahbuz State Nature Reserve, Eldar Shami State Nature Reserve and others. There are also nature reserves in the Sheki-Zagatala re-

gion, which has an important place in the field of ecotourism: Zagatala State Nature Reserve, Ilisu State Nature Reserve, Turyanchay State Nature Reserve.

Zagatala State Nature Reserve was founded in 1929. The reserve covers the Zagatala and Balakan administrative districts, as well as the southern micro-slopes of the central part of the Greater Caucasus Mountains and borders with the Republic of Georgia. By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 370s dated October 17, 2008, the territory of the reserve was increased to 47,349 hectares. In 1950, a department was established in the reserve to lead scientific research, which conducts studies on international biological problems. The territory of Zagatala State Nature Reserve consists of forests, sub-alpine and alpine meadows and high cliffs. There are more than 1000 species of plants in the reserve. The beech, oak, hornbeam, linden, ash, chestnut, walnut, hook pine and other tree species are found in the forests. However, there are also plant species in the forests, such as Caucasian dates, yew, Turkish hazel and wingnut, which are included in the Red Book. 32 species of mammals from the zoo world live here. Thus, there are more than 4,500 East Caucasian goats, 1,000 deer, 700 chamois and about 2,000 wild boars in the reserve. We rarely come across animals such as mountain bulls and roe deer. There are also 89 species of birds in the reserve. The Zagatala reserve is also inhabited by Caucasian snowcock, tetra birds, vultures, bearded vulture, falcon, and hawk listed in the Red Book.

Ilisu State Nature Reserve was established by the decision of the Government of Azerbaijan No. 57 of February 20, 1987 and the area of the reserve was extended to 17,381.6 hectares in 2003 by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated March 31, 2003. The reserve is located on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus - in the Gakh region, between the Zagatala and Ismayilli reserves. The name of the reserve is taken from the village of Ilisu in the Gakh region, and the name of the village was associated with a nearby spring. Due to the fact that the water of the spring is sulfur, the place was named Ilisu, which means "scented water". Mountain-meadow, mountain-meadow-forest, brown mountain-forest, humus-carbonate mountain-forest and brown mountain-forest soils are widespread in the territory of Ilisu reserve. In the area, there are plant species such as Orient beech, Caucasian hornbeam, blackberry, oriental oak, hips, birdpear, rock cotoneaster, wild cherry, cornel, raspberry. The reserve is home to 35 species of mammals, including ungulates, carnivorans, rodents and insectivorans. For example, the noble deer, roe deer, chamois, wild boar, brown bear, wolf, fox, stone and forest squirrels, least weasel, badger, wildcat, lynx, rabbit, dormouse, mouse, squirrel, white-toothed shrew, shrew hedgehog, horseshoe bat and others can be shown. It is noted that about 90 species of birds and 12 species of reptiles live in the Ilisu reserve. There are 5 species of amphibians in the reserve. The plants such as yew, Radde maple, the ungulates such as deer and roe deer, the kinds of birds such as tetra birds and bearded vulture such as birds are listed in the Red Book.

Turyanchay State Nature Reserve is located in the territory of Agdash, Oguz, Yevlakh and Gabala regions, and the main part is in the Akharbahar range of Bozdag in the south of Gabala region. It was established by the decision of the Government of Azerbaijan dated May 6, 1958 and the area was doubled by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated January 3 in 2003. At present, the area of the reserve is 22,488 hectares. There are more than 60 species of trees and shrubs in Turyanchay State Nature Reserve. The plants such as pistachio, ash, iberian oak, hybrid poplar, willow, iberia birch, Caucasian hackberry, barbed dog-rose, sea-buckthorn, a pomegranate, jasmine, smoke tree are the best examples of this. 112 species of birds, 24 species of mammals, 20 species of reptiles and 7 species of amphibians are found in the reserve (Zagatala State Nature Reserve Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/index.php?ln=az&pg=107>; Ilisu State Nature Reserve Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/index.php?ln=az&pg=103>; Mammadov, 2012, pp 220-221; İbrahimov, 2011, pp 117).

Establishment of sanctuaries and their main activities in Sheki-Zagatala region

There are other reserves which protect nature in different regions of the country. It is called sanctuary. There are also Sheki State Sanctuary, Zagatala State Sanctuary, Gabala State Sanctuary, Gakh State Sanctuary in the north-west. Each sanctuary has a specific purpose. Objectives such as the protection of the landscape of the southern slopes of the Greater Caucasus Mountains, the protection of fauna in the Ajinohur plain and the increase of endangered animals, the conservation of biological diversity are the main activities of these protected areas in ecosystem protection. Sheki State Nature Reserve was established on February 26, 1964 in Sheki region and is located in the Ayrichay basin between Yevlakh-Sheki and Sheki-Oguz highways. The total area of the reserve is 10,350 hectares. There are forest areas of oak, alder, walnut and mulberry trees in the reserve, and hawthorn, medlar, blackberry and plum bushes in the river valleys. In Sheki State Sanctuary brown bear, wild boar, wolf, jackal, fox, wildcat, raccoon, badger, rabbit, forest squirrel, squirrel such as animals, pheasant, black francolin, forest pigeon, pigeon, quail, greens birds lived. Zagatala State Sanctuary was established in November 2008 on an area of 6,557 hectares. Gabala State Sanctuary was established in 1993 in the Gabala region and covers an area of 39,700 hectares. Gakh State Sanctuary was established on June 16, 2003 and covers an area of 36,836 hectares (Sheki State Sanctuary Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/seki-dovlet-tebiet-yasaqligi>; Zagatala State Sanctuary Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/zaqatala-dovlet-tebiet-yasaqligi>; Gabala State Sanctuary Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/qebele-dovlet-tebiet-yasaqligi>; Gakh State Sanctuary Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/az/qax-dovlet-tebiet-yasaqligi>).

Importance of reserves and sanctuaries in Sheki-Zagatala region in the ecotourism sector

With its rich ecological environment, Azerbaijan has great potential in the field of ecotourism. The Republic of Azerbaijan is pursuing a successful policy in this area. The development of the “National Strategy

for the Protection and Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2017-2020” by the Decree No. 2358 of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan İlham Aliyev dated October 3, 2016 is one of the successful steps taken in the field of ecotourism. The priority of the National Strategy Plan is to preserve biodiversity in the country as a whole. The Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the coordinating body for the implementation of the National Strategy. According to the action plan of the Ministry, awareness-raising activities in this sector, restoration and preservation of biological diversity, creation and expansion of specially protected natural areas and other issues have been addressed (“*National Strategy for the Protection and Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2017-2020 years*” Retrieved from <https://eqanun.az/framework/33817>). As a result, much attention is paid to the protection of the country's biological environment.

Sheki-Zagatala region is one of the important places in the field of ecotourism in our country. In general, forest resources in the region are the basis of biodiversity. The fauna of the region is also diverse. Thus, the establishment of reserves and sanctuaries in the region, the expansion of their territories is part of this successful policy. At present, the protection of these areas and the prevention of the destruction of flora and fauna within them create conditions for the enrichment of the ecological environment in the Sheki-Zagatala region. It, in turn, paves the way for the region's success in ecotourism. Certainly, the more diverse and colorful the bio and zoo world of a region, the more it attracts tourists. It creates conditions for the revival of ecological tourism. Thus, the presence of reserves and sanctuaries creates conditions for the enrichment of flora and fauna, which leads to the development of ecotourism, and the development of ecotourism from the socio-economic and cultural point of view of the country.

Conclusion and suggestions

As a result, the Sheki-Zagatala region is considered one of the most important areas for the development of the Azerbaijani ecotourism sector, and reserves and sanctuaries are very important in this area. Thus, the following conclusions were drawn from the article:

- Nature reserves and sanctuaries in the Sheki-Zagatala part of the country play a key role in nature protection and their working principle plays a decisive role in environmental problems;
- Forest cover is deteriorating over time as a result of natural disasters and anthropogenic impacts. Establishment of reserves and sanctuaries in the area and carrying out works in this area contribute to the expansion of vegetation;
- Fauna, which is another living thing in nature, lives a hard life in forests. The existence of reserves and sanctuaries provides protection for mammals, birds, as well as reptiles and amphibians in the Sheki-Zagatala region. However, the process of reproduction of endangered animals allows the zoo to expand;
- Reserves and sanctuaries in the Sheki-Zagatala region, in addition to protecting nature, also

clean the ecological environment of the area, causing the regulation of ecological balance;

- The establishment of reserves and sanctuaries also has a positive impact on the Sheki-Zagatala ecotourism sector. Thus, the restoration of the ecological environment in the region creates a basis for the development of ecotourism;

- Further improvement of the Sheki-Zagatala ecological environment creates a basis for the influx of local and foreign visitors to the area. As a result, the development of ecotourism in the region has a positive impact on the ecotourism sector in the country;

- Also, the progress of the Sheki-Zagatala region in the field of ecotourism contributes to the socio-economic and cultural development of its territory.

On the other hand, given the steps taken to develop ecotourism in the region, we consider it appropriate to make a few recommendations on reserves and sanctuaries:

- Sheki-Zagatala region is very rich in flora and fauna. Therefore, in order to expand the field of ecotourism, to continue measures to prevent danger events and activities in these areas;

- In order to protect the ecological balance of Sheki-Zagatala, in addition to the reserves and sanctuaries in the area, other green zones and forests need

control. Each of these resources contributes to the rise of ecotourism;

- To inform people, as well as local and foreign tourists about the reserves and sanctuaries in the area and increase environmental knowledge in the field;

- Carry out certain work on world recognition of reserves and sanctuaries in Sheki-Zagatala region;

- To organize information bases such as brochures, information booklets on observance of rules and regulations of reserves and sanctuaries in the region;

- To pay special attention to environmental education and upbringing among schoolchildren, including students, about the importance of nature reserves and sanctuaries in the region for our ecology, and to expand the existing work in this regard.

Thus, we are aimed at showing the importance of reserves and sanctuaries for the development of ecological environment and ecotourism in the Sheki-Zagatala region in the paper.

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